

maximum yield of 20.3% was obtained when the reactants were heated at 140° for 6 hr in presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride

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A New Method for Resolution of Racemic forms of α -Amino acids and Related Compounds

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It has now been discovered that racemic forms of α -amino acids, their esters and in general, compounds containing an active amino group (e.g. threoamine) can be resolved by interaction with simple quinone molecules under suitable conditions to give monosubstituted quinonoid products of which the *d*-form separates completely during the reaction period leaving the *l*-form in solution.¹

X = H or halogen

Verification of the above results was accomplished by interaction of *p*-quinones with pure *d*- or *l*-forms and comparison with the above results using thin layer chromatographic technique, m ps, mixed m ps and optical rotation measurements. The reactions were carried out with *dl*-alanine, *dl*-valine, *dl*-isoleucine, *dl*-aspartic acid, and *dl*-tryptophane, and *d*-alanine on large scale laboratory amounts, with *dl*-alanine, to assure its successfulness as a new method for resolution of racemic forms of α -amino acids and related amino compounds.

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Isolation of an Antibacterial compound, Xanthumin from the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn.

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XANTHIUM strumarium Linn (Compositae), commonly known as 'Chhota Gokharu' in Hindi and 'Cocklebar' in English is an annual herb which grows wildly throughout India upto an altitude of

l-form in solution
d-form insoluble

It is to be pointed out that interaction of amino-compounds with quinones of the type (I) gives normally the 2,5-disubstituted products and in no case could the monosubstituted products be isolated^{2,3}. However, with racemic forms or with single optically active compounds only monosubstituted quinonoid products are formed under suitable ratios of reactants, probably because the optically active quinonoid molecule of type (II) is chemically less reactive, that it does not react further under the applied reaction conditions. The monosubstituted reaction products (II) were hydrolysed to give pure *d*- or *l*- α -amino acids by refluxing with concentrated mineral acids.

7,000 ft. The plant is used as diaphoretic and sedative. Its root is used as a bitter tonic and in the treatment of cancer and strumous diseases¹.

The seed fat of this plant has been thoroughly investigated by several workers^{2,3,4}. Plourde and Mockle⁵ have isolated Xanthinin from the leaves of Canadian *X. strumarium* while Minnato and Horibe⁶ have reported the isolation of a stereoisomer of Xanthinin from Japanese *X. strumarium* which they named as Xanthumin. No phytochemical work seems to have been done on the leaves of Indian *X. strumarium*, the petroleum ether extract of which was reported earlier to be active against gram positive

bacteria⁷. It was, therefore, considered of interest to carry out systematic investigations on this plant.

The present paper deals with the isolation and structural elucidation of the active principle responsible for antibacterial activity from the petroleum ether extract of the leaves of this plant.

Experimental

Green leaves of the plant were collected from Terai-region (Pantnagar, District Naini Tal, India), dried in shade and finely powdered. The powder was Soxhletted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) for about 24 hr. The extract was left overnight in a refrigerator when crystals separated out, which were dissolved in ether and charcoalised. The ethereal solution on concentration afforded colourless crystals which were recrystallised from an ether-alcohol mixture (4:1 V/V) to afford colourless shining crystals melting at 100°-101° (Found: C, 66.60%; H, 7.05%; C₁₇H₂₂O₃ requires: C, 66.65%; H, 7.25%). The yield of the compound ranges from 0.5 to 0.7% based on the dry weight of the leaves.

The I.R. spectrum of this compound indicated the presence of a γ -Lactonic carbonyl (1756 cm⁻¹), an acetate carbonyl (1735 cm⁻¹) and a ketonic carbonyl (1721 cm⁻¹). The m.p. was found to be identical with Xanthumin⁸, but different from the one reported for Xanthinin⁹. The identity of this compound as Xanthumin was further established by mixed melting point. R_f and I.R. spectrum were found to be identical with an authentic sample.

It is interesting to observe that Xanthumin is present in both the Indian and Japanese varieties of *X. strumarium* while Xanthinin has been found to be present in Canadian *X. strumarium*.

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Thermodynamic Formation Constants of Metal Chelates of Sulphadimethoxin Salicylaldimine

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IN continuation of our previous communications^{1,2} herein we describe potentiometric studies on complexes of sulphadimethoxin salicylaldimine (SUDMSA) with Copper (II), Nickel (II) and Cobalt (II) at 25°. The Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique^{3,4} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁵ has been applied to determine the protonation constant of the ligand and the formation constants of complexes. The log *k* values have been computed by least square method. Free energy changes and probability errors have also been evaluated.

These values at an ionic strength ($\mu = 0.2M$) are summarised in Table I.

Table I						
Ion	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log $\frac{K_1}{K_2}$	$\frac{\Delta G}{K \text{ cal/mole}}$	σ
H			log $\beta^H = 6.2$			
Cu(II)	5.50	3.42	8.92	2.08	-12.22	±.0005
Ni(II)	5.10	2.72	7.82	2.38	-10.66	±.001
Co(II)	4.03	2.22	6.24	1.80	-8.55	±.010

From the values of stability constants of the metal chelates the order is Cu > Ni > Co. This is in accordance with Irving and Williams.⁶

The large difference between successive formation constants may be attributed to the greater steric hindrance offered by SUDMSA as compared with the coordinated water molecule.

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